

Translation Errors in English-Indonesian President's Speech Text Produced by Students of the Sixth Semester of English Education Program at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate

Ririn Yastiawijaya
English Education Program, STKIP Kie Raha Ternate

Abstract

English students are always taught four language skills; listening, speaking, reading and writing. Besides the skills mentioned above, there is still one of the very important aspects encouraging the foreign language in teaching and learning process, namely translation. Thus, having ability in translation becomes a primary necessity for students who learn language especially foreign language. In Indonesia for example, English taught as a foreign language. However, there are often cases where translation contains errors and if there are errors in translation, the real message of the text is not communicated well. There could be misunderstanding because of error in translation. Based on the phenomenon, the researcher was interest to the research of the translation error. The researcher focused the research in the sixth semester student of English Education Program at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate consist of 31 students, because they have gotten the lectures of Translation, so at least they have already a bit knowledge. The data were taken from 18 students only as samples. The researcher collected the data by gave the students an English text to be translated into Indonesian. The research used descriptive qualitative method because the research attempted to find their errors in translating text. It means that the research aimed to find what kinds of error they might make. In analyzed the data, the researcher identified and classified the errors based on their types. The analysis of the data showed the student errors in translating English text. Based on the data analysis, the researcher found that the students committed errors in Omission (1700 or 97.3%), Misinformation (31 or 1.8%), and Addition (16 or 0.9%).

Keywords: *translation, translation error*

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1. Background

English students are always taught four language skills; listening, speaking, reading and writing. These skills are interrelated each other because each skill develop other skills. Besides the skills mentioned above, there is still one of the very important aspects encouraging the foreign language in teaching and learning process, namely translation. Thus, having ability in translation becomes a primary necessity for students who learn language especially foreign language. In Indonesia for example, English taught as a foreign language. Nowadays, many sources or learning materials are provided by a lot of experts, and most of them are written in English. The ability in translation is very useful to help student in understanding those material such article, journal, essay or even a

textbook. By learning translation, they can translate the English text or sentences into Indonesian or vice versa. People who do not have the same language can be connected by translation. Through translation they can understand any text that they read. Therefore, translation is important because it is a type of communication. However, there are often cases where translation contains errors and if there are errors in translation, the real message of the text is not communicated well. There could be misunderstanding because of error in translation. Based on the phenomenon that the researcher found, the researcher was interested in the research of Translation errors in STKIP Kie Raha Ternate. The researcher analyzed students' errors in translating an English-Indonesian president's speech text.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Definition of Translation

According to Newmark (1988:5) translation is rendering the meaning of a text into another language in the way that the author intended the text. Newmark gave more explanation from his statement above that translation was not only translating the language but also the translator should transfer the meaning of the text, so the reader knew about the author intention. He also states that translation is mastery in transferring written message from one language into written message of another language. Here, Newmark restricts the definition only in the scope written language.

Catford (1965: 1) states that translation is an operation performed on language, a process of substituting a text in one language for a text in another. Furthermore, Catford (1965:20) states that translation may be defined as the replacement of textual material in one language (source language) by equivalent textual material in another language (target language).

According to Brislin (1976:1) translation is a general term referring to the transfer of thoughts and ideas from one language (source) to another (target), whether the languages are in written or oral form.

In general, translation is changing a text from one language into another without changing the meaning or the idea that occur in the source language. Translation is consisting of changing from one state or form to another, to turn into one's own or another's language.

Basically, all statements above have the same ideas, in the sense that translation is a process of replacing or transferring messages, thoughts, ideas, meaning or information from the source language to the target language. The main point in the translation is that a translator may not change the meaning of the message of the original text.

2.2. Definition of Error

Learning something need a process in which success will come by profiting some errors. Error is systematic deviation, when a student has not mastered something and constantly got wrong. Concerning the theory of errors, many linguists have technical definitions to identify the errors.

Error is caused by lack of competence. Error is an act or condition of ignorant or imprudent deviation from a code behavior. Errors are systematic that their occurrence is in some way regular. In order to analyze errors in proper perspective, it is crucial to distinguish errors from mistake.

Brown (1987: 125) defines an error as a noticeable deviation from the adult grammar of native speaker, reflecting the inter language competence of the learner. While Richards (1997: 25) states that a learner's errors provides evidence of the system of the language that he is using (i.e. has learned) at a particular point in the course (and it must be repeated that he is using some systems, although it is not yet the right system).

2.3. Error in Translation

A translation error arises from the existence of a relationship between a Target Text and a Source Text during the transfer and movement from the Source Text to the Target Text. According to Baker (1992), Errors in translation mostly result from the non-equivalence between the source and target languages. However, good translators with encyclopedic knowledge and linguistic knowledge of both the source and target languages know how to deal with them; therefore, errors can indicate the quality of a translation; moreover, they can reveal what is going on in the translator's thinking process (Seguinot: 1990). While Wills (1982) describes a translation error as an offence against a norm in a linguistic contact situation.

From the definitions about translation errors above, we can conclude that there are many aspects involved in translating, not only how to translate the text meaningful but also translators must pay attention to the context related to the culture and conditions that the text can be applied.

2.3.1. The Types of Translation Error

According to Dulay, Burt, and Krashen (1982: 146) the most useful and commonly used as bases for the descriptive classification of errors is linguistic category, surface category and communicative effect taxonomy.

2.3.1.1. Linguistic Category

Linguistic category taxonomies classify errors according to either or both the language components or linguistic constituents. Language components include phonology (pronunciation), discourse and etc, while constituents include the elements that comprise each language component.

2.3.1.2. Surface Strategy Taxonomy

The categorizing of errors is according to how the surface structure of a sentence or expression is altered by the error. Such a classification would include omission, addition, misformation, and misordering.

a. Omission

Omission errors are characterized by the absence of an item that must appear in a well-formed utterance. An omission error occurs when an element of information in the source text is left out of the target text. Missing words or sentences within a passage may be marked as one or more errors of omission, depending on how much is omitted (words or sentences not translated). Leaving something out could change the message completely. The examples of omission:

A man dressed in an old grey overcoat. = Pria dengan jaket hujan berwarna abu-abu tua.

The sentence above is not well-formed. There is article 'a' in the source language and the student omits the article in the target language. The correct form of the sentence above is *Seorang pria dengan jaket hujan berwarna abu-abu tua.*

All the students who had returned from their vacation. = Semua siswa yang telah kembali dari liburan.

The sentence above is not well-formed. The student omits the possessive pronoun in the target language. The correct form of the sentence above is *Semua siswa yang telah kembali dari liburam mereka.*

b. Addition

Addition errors are the presence of an item that must not appear in well-formed utterances. Dulay, Burt and Krashen (1982: 156) say addition usually occurs in later stage of second language acquisition or when the learner has acquitted some target language

rule. An addition error also occurs when the translator introduces superfluous information or stylistic effects.

Sometimes, the translator adds additional information which does not exist in the source text. The examples of addition:

The drilling of natural gas and oil. = Pengeboran gas alam dan minyak bumi.

The sentence above is not well-formed. The student adds a word *bumi* in the target language. The correct form of the sentence above is *Pengeboran gas alam dan minyak*.

Every book which is written to deceive the reader. = Setiap buku yang ditulis untuk menipu pembacanya.

The sentence above is not well-formed. The student adds possessive pronoun *nya* in the target language. The correct form is *Setiap buku yang ditulis untuk menipu pembaca*.

c. Misinformation

Misinformation *error* is a type of error that is characterized by the use of incorrect morpheme or structure. It is considered to be the use of the wrong form of the morpheme or structure. For example:

The collision between a motorcycle and a car. = Gabungan antara motor dan mobil.

One of the characteristics of unduly free translation is replace the meaning of the source language. The student has replaced the meaning *collision* for the target language. The correct form sentence is *Tabrakan antara sepeda motor dan mobil*.

d. Misordering

Misordering error is error that is characterized by the incorrect placement of a morpheme or group morphemes in the sentences it means that error of misordering is marked by misordering for a morpheme or a group of morphemes in the sentence. For example:

The former prime minister, Sir William McMahon. = Sir William McMahon, pencetus perdana menteri.

The sentence above is not well-formed. The student misorders the noun phrases. The correct form sentence is *Pencetus perdana menteri, Sir William McMahon*.

2.3.1.3. Comparative Taxonomy

Comparative taxonomy classifies errors based on comparison between the structure of language learner errors and certain other types of construction. This classification is divided into four parts:

- 1) Developmental errors, these errors is like the errors made by the students learning the target language as their first language. For example, *dog eat it*.
- 2) Interlingual errors, this error is like in structure to a semantically equivalent phrase or sentence in the learner's native language. For example, *I visit temple Prambanan*. This is errors in using phrase, which the learner translate Indonesian language word for word into English language.
- 3) Ambiguous errors, this error reflect the learner's native language structure, and at the same time, they are of the type found in the speech of children acquiring a first language. This error equally well as developmental or interlingual. For example, *I no have a car*.

Other errors, this error is beside of the other types above such as developmental errors, interlingual errors, and ambiguous errors. For example, *she do hungry*.

2.4. Speech Text

2.4.1. Definition of Speech Text

Speech is the expression of the mind in the form of words addressed to the people (Depdiknas, 2005: 871), while the text of the speech is a text or script used by a person who gives a speech to convey ideas to the crowd. Speech Text is a form of one-way communication in the form of expression of ideas and thoughts of the speaker about a thing to many people and not gets directly from the listener.

Speech is an activity which a person is speaking in public. The speech aims to express his opinion to the authorities, or provide an idea of something that can affect other parties. Speech is generally done by a person who is giving speeches, general opinions, images and statements about an event that is important in life and deserves to be discussed people (the public). The purpose of the speech is to convey a certain information or idea. Before people make speeches, they usually arrange the speeches first.

Speeches are generally used by a country leader, group, or other to lead and speak in front of a general audience. A speech by a leader with good content can give a positive impression and a message for someone who listens to the speech. Speeches are activities undertaken to convey and impart ideas as well as the thoughts, information or ideas of the speaker to the people and aim to make the listener sure of the ideas that have been conveyed.

2.4.2. *The Aims of Speech*

These are five aims of speech, which is as follows:

- a. Encourage: Oral delivery with the aim of encouraging a speaker expects inspiring reactions, evokes the emotions of the listeners.
- b. Convincing: Speeches with the purpose of convincing this can mean that speakers seek to influence the mental or intellectual audiences. The speech activity in it uses argumentation. The submission of facts with concrete evidence and examples is to be applied, so that the expected reaction of the hearers is the conformity of opinion or belief in the material presented.
- c. Doing: The physical reaction (action) of the listener is the effect of the purpose of making a speech. The purpose of this speech can be chosen when the listener performs the action as desired by the speaker. Therefore, the speech with this purpose is persuasive.
- d. Notify: Oral descriptions aimed at informing is that the speaker wants to tell or to communicate something to the listener so that they can understand something, or to expand knowledge, from that understanding it can be categorized as speech with the aim of informing instructive or teachable speech.
- e. Fun: The purpose of this speech is to entertain listeners. Speeches of this type usually contain humor inserts. Humor becomes an important tool that cannot be separated when delivering verbal messages.

3. Method

3.1. *The Method of Study*

The researcher used the qualitative approach which involved the descriptive method in it. Bogdan and Taylor (1992: 21-22) stated that qualitative research is one of research procedures which produce descriptive data, that is utterance or scripts and behavior of the person we gazing at. Qualitative approach is expected to produce deep description about utterance, scripts, and behavior of a society or certain groups in a setting context from comprehensive and holistic view.

3.2. *Population and Sample*

According to McMillan and Schumacher in their book “Research in Education”, a Population is a group of elements or cases, whether individuals, objects, or events, that confirm to specific criteria and to which we intend to generalize the results of the research (1997:164). It means population is a number of individuals which have at least one characteristic in common.

The population of this study is the sixth semester students of the STIKIP Kie Raha in the academic year 2017/2018. The number of students is about 31.

Sample is part of the whole population from which the researcher takes the data. Suharsimi Arikunto (2002: 109) says that sample is the reflection of the population so that it should reflect all characteristics of the population. In this research, the researcher uses 18 out of the whole students of the sixth semester of English Education Program at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate in the academic year 2017/2018 as the sample of the research.

3.3. Technique of Collecting and Analyzing Data

The crucial step in doing a research is collecting the data. In this study, the researcher uses a test as the instrument of collecting data. The researcher gave students a President's speech texts in English form. The students were asked to translate the text into Indonesian. The students did the test. The students' worksheets were collected by the researcher. The errors were analyzed from the students' translation. It is done in order to find out what kinds of errors made by students and which kind errors mostly produced.

After the data were collected, these must be analyzed to achieve the intended objectives. The researcher's objectives are to find out what kinds of errors that made by students and which kind of error mostly made by the students in translating English text into Indonesian.

Based on the descriptive method applied in this study, the researcher, in analyzing the data of this study, will use the following procedure:

- ✓ Identify the errors.
- ✓ Classifying the errors based on their types.
- ✓ The researcher then used descriptive analysis technique (percentage) to analyze the data. The formula used is as follow:

$$\text{Error Percentage} = \frac{\text{The Number of Errors Each Category}}{\text{The Total Number of Error}} \times 100\%$$

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Data

Table 1
The Recapitulation of Students' Errors

Students	Types of Error		
	Omission	Addition	Misformation
Student 1	10	1	2
Student 2	106	-	2
Student 3	263	2	2
Student 4	14	-	1
Student 5	22	-	2
Student 6	18	-	-
Student 7	138	-	2
Student 8	247	-	1
Student 9	380	2	3
Student 10	8	2	5
Student 11	30	1	3
Student 12	34	1	2
Student 13	11	1	3
Student 14	30	1	-
Student 15	50	-	-
Student 16	227	-	1
Student 17	19	5	-
Student 18	93	-	2
Total	1700 errors	16 errors	31 errors
	1747 errors		

Percentage of students' errors

Omission

$$P = \frac{1700}{1747} \times 100\% = 97\%$$

Addition

$$P = \frac{16}{1747} \times 100\% = 1\%$$

Misformation

$$P = \frac{31}{1747} \times 100\% = 2\%$$

Table 2

Frequency of student' error

No.	Types of Errors	Frequency of Errors	Percentage (%)
1	Omission	1700	97
2	Misformation	31	2
3	Addition	16	1
Total		1747	100

Graphic 1

Based on the table of students' error, it can be stated that:

1. Total errors of Omission are 1700 errors on percentage 97%
2. Total errors of Misformation are 31 on percentage 2%
3. Total errors of Addition are 16 on percentage 1%

Table 3

Table of Students' who made Errors

No	Types of Errors	Number of Students'	Frequency of Errors
1	Omission	18	1700
2	Misformation	15	31
3	Addition	7	16

There were 18 students and 1700 committed in Omission area with 97%. It happened because the students did not translate words or omission. The students omitted necessary words such as “I mengundang mereka untuk makan siang dan makan malam”. If the student just put the word “I” in the TT, then she omitted that word because he did not translate in into the TT. “*saya*” in the correct one. The sentence should be like “Saya mengundang mereka untuk makan siang dan makan malam”.

There were 15 students and 31 errors committed in Misinformation area with 2%. It happened because the student might face difficulty in finding the right meaning of a word or just put it as they want. The student tended to change the meaning of some words from the ST into the TT. Actually, replace the real meaning of a word caused Misinformation in the TT such as “Kami ingin membongkar 24 pelabuhan laut...”, the right form should be “Kami ingin membangun 24 pelabuhan laut...” because the real meaning of “to build” is “membangun”.

There were 7 students and 16 errors committed in Addition area with 1%. They added additional information or unnecessary item in the sentence where it does not exist in the source text such as “We want to build sea toll” is the TT. The students translated it into “Kami juga ingin membangun tol laut” in the TT. It means that the students added word “juga” in the TT where it does not exist in the ST.

4.2. Interpretation

Based on the data analysis, the researcher found that the students committed errors in Omission (1700 or 97.3%), Misinformation (31 or 1.8%), and Addition (16 or 0.9%). From those frequencies, the researcher sees that most of students are still made the error when translating English text into Indonesian. It also shows that the most errors that produced by the students in this research is Omission. According to Dulay, this type of error is often made by students in learning English because when they do not pay attention to the ST well, it is possible if they will omit some words, and they also do not translate some words just because they do not know what the meaning of it.

From the explanation above, the researcher concludes that the types of errors which are always produced by the students are including to Omission error, Misinformation error and Addition error. And based on the frequency, the type of error that mostly produced by the students of the sixth semester of English Department at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate is Omission error.

5. Conclusion

After analyzing the data translation of presiden's speech text produced by the student of of the sixth semester of English Education Program at STKIP KIE RAHA TERNATE, the researcher found many errors. As the finding, the researcher found three kinds of error in translating the English-Indonesian presidenets's speech text. They are omission error, addition error and misformation errors. The numbers of omission errors are 1700 (97%). The number of addition errors is 16 (1%). While the number of misinformation errors are 31 (2%). So, it means that the kind of error that is mostly produced by the students is omission error (1700 errors / 97%).

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About Author:

The researcher, Ririn Yastiwijaya is the first child from parents Parman Nahar and Adeina Abdurrahim, was born in Topo, Tidore on 28 October 1995 and now stay in Sasa. The researcher had a Sister named Rizqiah Mardiana, and two brothers, they are Fakhrul Rizki and Fardhan As Parman. The researcher started her school at SDN 1 Topo, and then continued her study at Mts Al-Ikhwan seli. After finished her junior high school, the researcher continued at MAN Gurabati in Scince Program. Graduated from high school, the researcher ever studied at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate in English Education Program and finished her study there.